

Best Practice Recommendations: Research Imaging IG CHECKLIST

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Introduction

Imaging plays a critical role in improving patient outcomes. This guidance document describes best practices for the secure, ethical and efficient sharing of imaging data for research purposes. Its aim is to support researchers and organisations in enabling high-quality imaging studies while meeting all the relevant scientific, ethical, legal, and information-governance requirements.

Imaging data has key distinctions from other datasets (Table 1) and presents distinct challenges that are not fully addressed by standard data governance frameworks. Unlike structured or tabular data, imaging data is high-dimensional, context-dependent, and often undergoes complex transformations prior to analysis. As a result, governance decisions directly influence not only privacy risk, but also data quality, analytical validity, and research outcomes.

Embedded identifiers beyond metadata	Identifiable information may exist not only in metadata (e.g., DICOM headers) but also within the image itself (e.g., burned-in text, facial features), requiring both metadata and pixel-level de-identification approaches.
Transformation through de-identification	De-identification is not a neutral process; it can alter image characteristics, remove clinically meaningful features, or introduce artefacts, impacting downstream analysis.
Context-dependent data quality	Image quality is multi-dimensional and must be defined relative to the intended research use. Variability in acquisition, reconstruction, and preprocessing can introduce bias or confounding effects.
Dependence on metadata for interpretation and reuse	Imaging data is highly reliant on associated metadata (e.g., acquisition parameters, scanner type, protocols) for interpretation, harmonisation, and reproducibility. Removal or modification of this metadata can significantly reduce research utility.
Complex data pipelines and environments	Imaging research typically involves multi-stage pipelines (ingestion, transformation, analysis) across specialised environments such as Trusted Research Environments (TREs), increasing the need for transparency, auditability, and reproducibility.
Interdependence of governance, quality, and usability	Decisions relating to governance (e.g., anonymisation, access controls) are tightly coupled with data quality and usability, and cannot be treated as separate concerns.

Table 1: Imaging data distinctions

These characteristics mean that applying standard data governance approaches without adaptation may result in either:

- excessive restriction, limiting research value, or
- insufficient control, increasing privacy or ethical risk

Accordingly, imaging research governance requires a risk-proportionate, context-aware approach that explicitly considers the interaction between data protection, data quality, and research utility.

These best practice recommendations reflect both published evidence and real-world operational experience of imaging research across the quadruple innovation helix of NHS, academic, industry, third-sector and public/citizen settings. They are based on a series of previous work outputs, including analysis of multi-stakeholder workshops, literature review and case studies. Prior work has been published under creative commons (4.0) licence and is freely available on the BESTIES Zenodo community site (<https://zenodo.org/communities/besties/records>).

Implementation Expectations

This guidance should be applied at project initiation and revisited throughout the data lifecycle.

Organisations should identify responsible individuals for:

- data quality
- de-identification
- governance compliance

Outputs should include:

- documented processes
- reproducible pipelines
- auditable decisions

Figure 1: Implementation Expectations

Definitions

Where a research analysis environment could be named or described as; a Secure Data Environment (SDE), Trusted Research Environment (TRE), Safe Haven, Virtual Data Enclave, Virtual Research Centre, or similar, and whether on premise, cloud-based or hybrid; for the purposes of this guide, the general term TRE will be used.

Anonymisation - The process of making personally identifiable data anonymous so that individuals can no longer be identified, including by using or linking to, publicly available data. In contrast to **Pseudonymisation**, true anonymisation cannot be reversed.

De-identification – Removal or replacement of personal identifiers, or potential identifiers, so that it would be difficult to reestablish a link between the individual and their data

DICOM - Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (global, vendor-neutral standard for handling, storing, printing, and transmitting information in medical imaging)

DPA 2018 – Data Protection Act 2018

DPO – Data Protection Officer

GDPR – UK General Data Protection Regulation

HDRUK – Health Data Research UK (<https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/>)

HPC – High Performance Computing

HRA – Health Research Authority (<https://www.hra.nhs.uk/>)

IG – Information Governance

MHRA - Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency

MRC – Medical Research Council (<https://www.ukri.org/councils/mrc/>)

NIHR – National Institute for Health and Care Research (<https://www.nihr.ac.uk/>)

NHS – UK National Health Service

NSIA 2021 – National Security and Investment Act 2021

PSD – Project Specification Document

Pseudonymisation – The replacement of direct identifiers within a dataset with pseudonyms so that the data no longer directly identifies individuals. In contrast to **Anonymisation**, pseudonymisation provides the option of reinstating the original identifiers should they be needed and also allows for the linking of datasets through the creation of common pseudonyms.

SATRE - Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (<https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/index.html>)

SDE – Secure Data Environment

TRE – Trusted Research Environment

UKRI – UK Research and Innovation (<https://www.ukri.org/>)

UKRIO - UK Research Integrity Office (<https://ukrio.org/>)

Stakeholders

- Researchers and research teams (clinical, academic, translational)
- Research Funders (e.g., NIHR, MRC, UKRI, Wellcome Trust, UKRI-funded)

- Institutional governance bodies examples:
 - IG teams
 - Research Governance teams
 - Research and Innovation Contract teams
 - Cyber security personnel
 - Research integrity office
 - DPOs
 - Data management division (e.g., libraries in academia, data management/research informatics/data warehousing/clinical imaging in NHS)
 - Governance and security departments for compliance with Trusted Research (NSIA 2021)
 - Ethics committee governing body
- Infrastructure Providers:
 - TRE managers and operators
 - Platforms teams
- External stakeholders and partners examples:
 - Funded groups/bodies: [BioFAIR](#) (BBSRC-funded), [Elixir](#)
 - UKRIO
 - HRA
 - MHRA
 - Public/Citizens
 - HDRUK

Scope

This guidance applies to the management and provision of imaging data and, where appropriate, sharing and/or transfer, for research purposes across academic, clinical, and industry-collaborative settings. It covers:

- Best practices for secure and compliant image sharing
- Roles and responsibilities across organisational boundaries
- Ethical and legal considerations, including data protection and Trusted Research requirements
- Practical recommendations for enabling reproducible, high-quality imaging research

It does **not** prescribe specific technical platforms or mandate particular technologies; instead, it provides principles and considerations that can be applied across diverse organisational contexts.

Synthetic data and synthetically-created images are still within scope. The same governance considerations apply to synthetic data which has been generated from personal data, as per the HRA.

Currently Out of Scope

Generative AI is a rapidly evolving area of research, which requires its own discrete considerations and is not specifically addressed within this guidance.

Special cases:

Special or unusual cases such as in the case of facial images or the potential ability to reconstruct facial images are not yet covered by this guidance.

Evidence-Informed Principles

This guidance is informed by a synthesis of published literature and multi-stakeholder workshop findings conducted through the BESTIES programme. Across both sources, imaging research challenges were consistently identified as arising from the interaction between:

- data quality and heterogeneity
- de-identification and transformation processes
- governance frameworks and interpretation
- infrastructure and organisational constraints

These findings demonstrate that imaging data is not inherently research-ready, and that variability in acquisition, metadata, and processing can significantly impact analytical validity and reproducibility. Furthermore, governance and de-identification processes actively shape the structure and usability of imaging data, rather than acting as neutral safeguards. Imaging research should be understood as a socio-technical system, where technical, governance, and operational decisions are interdependent.

Accordingly, this guidance adopts a risk-proportionate, lifecycle-based approach, recognising that decisions relating to image preparation, anonymisation, access, and reuse directly impact research validity, reproducibility, and trust.

This guidance document describes the considerations to be reviewed for imaging research projects, specifically the principles of: Data Protection, Data Quality and Sustainability.

Principles

Research Context: What is the research question and justification for the imaging methods, data and environment proposed.

1. Data Protection

Risk Proportionate approach to designing security measures:

- Define the threat risk (intentional breaches by internal and external threat actors, and unintentional data leakage)
- Consider the likelihood of each type of threat
- Assess the damage each threat risk would cause and remedial and regulatory actions which would be required for each. Damage includes operational capability, reputation, loss of trust and financial impact.
- Based on the above state the min. required security measures
- Environment: Risk is determined by both the data itself and the surrounding environment (context).

Figure 2: Determining risk

Define **roles and responsibilities**, permissions for security

- Decide how these should be defined e.g., by system, data asset or other approach

- Consider roles and responsibilities throughout the data lifecycle (see Section 4)

Procedures for anonymisation, monitoring/testing and storing data

- Risk based approach to de-identification should be applied so that:
 - All attributes of images are evaluated for potential identifiers, including metadata and burned-in text and overlays. Clinically meaningful features and metadata essential to data provenance must be retained*
 - Processes should exist for handling datasets where de-identification cannot be achieved without adversely affecting the integrity of the image. E.g., redaction of the entire imaging series during de-identification.
- De-identification processes must be transparently reported and retained to maintain the scientific integrity of the image and enable reproducibility**
- Personal data classification within the context of the anonymisation process e.g., at which point is data considered anonymised and therefore outside the scope of the GDPR and DPA 2018.
- Method for moving, sharing, accessing, analysing and storing data.
- De-identification processes should include formal validation steps, including:
 - testing on representative datasets
 - verification of removal of identifiable information
 - assessment of impact on image quality and usability
- Organisations should maintain records of de-identification decisions, including:
 - methods used
 - parameters applied
 - known limitations
- Where possible, re-identification risk assessments should be conducted and documented, particularly for rare conditions or small datasets
- De-identification approaches should be consistent across collaborating organisations, or differences explicitly documented and justified

*note that this could have implications around storage and the methodologies used – particularly where the number of image studies and slices is very high.

**if using random number generation, reproducibility, in terms of producing the same pseudonymisation (e.g., where you have multiple images that need to be attributed to the same subject), will often be foiled unless the pipeline and methodologies are designed with this in

mind. If the pseudonymised number will not matter for reproducibility, then this extra consideration will not be needed.

Evidence-Based Considerations

Evidence from the literature and workshop findings indicates that de-identification is not a neutral preprocessing step, but a transformative process which may alter image characteristics, metadata integrity, and downstream analytical validity.

DICOM metadata contains critical contextual information required for data provenance, harmonisation, and reproducibility; however, its removal or modification can significantly limit research utility. Similarly, pixel-level de-identification techniques, such as removal of burned-in text or masking, may inadvertently remove clinically meaningful features or introduce artefacts.

Variation in anonymisation approaches across organisations further introduces inconsistency, limiting reproducibility and cross-site comparability (Clunie et al., 2025; Pei et al., 2025). Workshop findings reinforce that governance decisions are often locally interpreted, creating additional variability in implementation.

In particular:

- Removal or modification of DICOM metadata may reduce the ability to assess data provenance, harmonise datasets, or evaluate bias
- Pixel-level de-identification (e.g., removal of burned-in text or masking) may alter clinically meaningful features
- Variation in anonymisation approaches across organisations introduces inconsistency and limits reproducibility

Best Practice Recommendations

- De-identification strategies should be risk-proportionate and use-case specific, balancing privacy risk against research utility
- Metadata required for reproducibility, linkage, and bias assessment should be retained where possible and justified where removed
- De-identification pipelines should be:
 - documented
 - version-controlled

- validated using representative datasets
- reproducible
- Organisations should implement testing and validation processes, including human review and benchmark datasets, to ensure that de-identification does not adversely affect research outcomes

2. Data Quality

Relevant: Context of the research question. Valuable for research, whilst maintaining necessary precautions.

- Does the data collection enable all outcomes of the study to be met?
- If collecting data from other databases (such as MACRO or RedCAP), have you considered and points of vulnerability where data could be misaligned or misreported? If using ciphers or pseudo-identifiers, how will you ensure matching data points.
- How will the datasets be future-proofed? i.e., data dictionaries or excel output templates so details can be reviewed by different researchers at different dates?
- Does the method of upload ensure all metadata integrity for any possible / reasonable analysis.

PSD – Project Specification Document list

- Description of data to be collected/used for research purposes.
- Example list of data
- Description of DICOM tags to be used, private vs public

Data provenance

- Is there a flag system in place, how are deletions/corrections managed? Are there crosschecks with study data and site information for missing data or incomplete data?
- Auditability of data
- How many times has it been used?
- Movement of data through data pipelines e.g., into HPC or a TRE, who has access to the data, what software tools have been used for processing, etc.
- Projects should define minimum quality thresholds aligned to the intended use (e.g., clinical interpretation vs AI training vs validation)
- Quality assessment processes should be:

- applied consistently across datasets
- reproducible
- documented
- Where automated quality assessment tools are used:
 - their performance and limitations should be understood
 - their impact on dataset composition should be evaluated
- Datasets should be assessed for systematic bias introduced by quality variation, including:
 - site-specific differences
 - acquisition protocol variation
 - demographic or clinical skew
- Annotation processes should include:
 - clear guidelines
 - inter-observer validation where possible
 - documentation of uncertainty

Evidence-Based Considerations

Across radiology, ophthalmology, and digital pathology, image quality is consistently identified as:

- multi-dimensional
- context-dependent
- a potential source of bias

Variability in acquisition, reconstruction, and preprocessing can lead to hidden confounding effects, where models learn artefacts or site-specific characteristics rather than underlying clinical signals.

Radiological imaging is particularly sensitive to acquisition and reconstruction variability, including noise, artefacts, and compression, all of which may affect downstream analysis. In ophthalmology, image quality is influenced by acquisition conditions such as motion and illumination, and automated quality assessment methods may introduce bias if exclusion criteria are not carefully managed. In digital pathology, artefacts such as staining variability and focus inconsistencies significantly impact both human interpretation and AI performance.

Annotation and metadata quality are also critical determinants of dataset usability, with inconsistent labelling and incomplete metadata contributing to reduced reproducibility.

Workshop findings further demonstrate that:

- ‘quality’ is often undefined and inconsistently applied
- metadata completeness is critical but frequently lacking
- quality filtering may introduce bias if not transparently applied

Best Practice Recommendations

- Image quality should be defined as fitness-for-purpose, explicitly linked to the research question
- Quality assessment should include:
 - technical measures (e.g., resolution, artefacts)
 - dataset characteristics (e.g., representativeness, completeness)
 - annotation quality and consistency
- Decisions to exclude or enhance data should be:
 - documented
 - justified
 - reproducible
- Metadata standards should be defined at project outset, including:
 - required DICOM tags
 - provenance tracking
 - transformation history

3. Sustainability

Skills, resources, funding and technical solutions must be fit for purpose for a particular project.

Prior to new projects:

- i. Determine technical capacity required for the project and ensure that there are adequate funds and other resources to meet this (e.g., access to HPC within working hours, availability of extraction tools).
- ii. Determine the necessary skills and knowledge required to successfully execute the project. Ensure skills gaps are identified and addressed.

Minimising bias, analysing bias/representative

- Characteristics of datasets are defined to enable judgements to be made on the representativeness of the data for a particular project e.g., demographic, geographic, genetic, and disease representation
- Datasets may be unusable for further research due to the lack of necessary characteristics to enable bias judgements to be made, either through deidentification or lack of initial data collection or linkage.

Data as an asset:

- Data sovereignty is defined, documenting ownership, access rights, licensing terms, and usage restriction, and the documentation accompanies the dataset throughout the data lifecycle.
- Consent for data collection and re-use is documented and accessible, and in accordance with participant consent and favourable opinion of a recognised ethical review body.
- Regulatory considerations on data such as geographic restrictions on data locations and sharing related to GDPR
- Permissions (or denial of permission) for data to be shared and reused for commercial research purposes e.g., commercial drug & medical device development
- Datasets should include sufficient contextual information to enable reuse, including:
 - acquisition parameters
 - preprocessing steps
 - de-identification methods
- Data access conditions should be clearly defined and consistently applied, including:
 - permitted uses
 - restrictions
 - governance requirements
- Where feasible, datasets should be designed to support:
 - cross-site use
 - interoperability with existing platforms
- Long-term storage and access strategies should consider:
 - sustainability of infrastructure
 - cost implications
 - responsibility for maintenance

Evidence-Based Considerations

Both literature and workshop findings highlight that imaging datasets are frequently not reusable due to:

- poor documentation
- difficult to interpret without contextual metadata
- Constraints from unclear ownership and licensing arrangements

Literature further emphasises the importance of:

- FAIR principles
- lifecycle governance
- long-term infrastructure planning

The FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) are widely recognised as essential for enabling sustainable data reuse, yet implementation remains inconsistent across imaging research environments.

Infrastructure constraints, including limitations in storage, compute, and interoperability, further restrict the scalability and reuse of imaging datasets.

Best Practice Recommendations

- Imaging data should be treated as a long-term asset, with clearly defined:
 - defined ownership
 - licensing conditions
 - reuse permissions
- Data lifecycle considerations should include:
 - creation and ingestion
 - transformation (including de-identification)
 - storage and access
 - reuse and destruction
- Documentation (e.g., PSD, data dictionaries, processing logs) should be:
 - maintained
 - accessible

- linked to datasets

Adoption of FAIR principles should be embedded across the image, environment and project lifecycle to support reuse and interoperability.

4. Cross-Cutting Considerations

Evidence from both literature and stakeholder workshops demonstrates that imaging research operates as a socio-technical system, where data quality, de-identification, governance, and infrastructure are interdependent and that the following considerations apply across all principles:

- **Interdependency:** Data quality, de-identification, and governance decisions are interdependent and should not be considered in isolation. Decisions relating to these factors should be considered together, recognising their interdependencies.
- **Standardisation vs flexibility:** While standard approaches are required to enable scalability, governance and technical decisions must remain adaptable to context
- **Transparency:** Documentation of data transformations, governance decisions, and analytical processes is essential for reproducibility and trust
- **Risk proportionality:** Governance measures should reflect the sensitivity, scale, and intended use of the data
- **Operational feasibility:** Implementation must account for real-world constraints, including infrastructure, skills, and organisational processes. Where multiple organisations are involved, alignment of processes and expectations should be agreed early.
- **Trade-offs** should be explicitly documented during projects, including:
 - privacy vs utility
 - quality vs inclusion
 - standardisation vs flexibility
- **Governance and technical processes** should be designed to be proportionate to risk, avoiding unnecessary barriers to research
- **Practical implementation considerations** (e.g., procurement, infrastructure constraints, timelines) should be accounted for when applying this guidance

Roles and Responsibilities

Named organisational roles and positions will vary, however there should be at least one person fitting the following roles with delegated responsibilities. Using the SATRE role definitions (<https://satre-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/roles.html>):

Project Roles

Role name	Role description	Responsibilities
Data Consumer	General term for any individuals who will be provided access to data via a TRE.	Checking the data provided matches what was requested and agreed and that it has been provided in a pseudonymised, appropriate manner. Reporting any breaches of privacy in the data provided as soon as they are identified. Ensuring conduct, behaviours and data processing tasks adhere to the data consumer agreements. Preparing research outputs in a manner consistent with the data consumer agreements and performing an initial check for disclosure control purposes prior to requesting their release.
Data Analyst	Specific term for people provided access to data via a TRE, who intend to carry out analysis or conduct research using the data. These could be programmers and data scientists, but could also be scientists working in fields where deep computing expertise is less common. Analysts working with TREs that meet the SATRE standard should have a broadly similar user experience, at least where the type of analyst is consistent (e.g. data scientists). This includes both the user experience of the platforms themselves, and the associated documentation.	Analysis and processing of images in a suitable, provided environment. Preparing research outputs in a manner consistent with the data consumer agreements and performing an initial check for disclosure control purposes prior to requesting their release.
Project Manager	The person in charge of coordinating other roles for the duration of a specific TRE project. See Project and programme management.	Ensuring provision of images is appropriate to the project and delivered in a suitable environment.
Project Team	Refers to the team of data analysts and project manager(s) working on a specific project that uses a TRE.	Ensuring at all times that any images requested for a project are appropriately provided, pseudonymised/anonymised, analysed and processed.

Table 2: Project Roles

Data Management Roles

Role name	Role description	Responsibilities
Data Steward	People who ensure data within a TRE is maintained and processed in ways useful to data analysts, including providing data extracts. May also be known as Data Wranglers, Data Engineers or Data Cleaners.	Ensuring images are appropriately pseudonymised
Database Administrator	People responsible for managing any databases included in the TRE. Where a database is used by multiple projects, this includes handling segregation of	Images are appropriately stored, catalogues, indexed and retrievable

	users and databases belonging to different projects. See Advanced Computing Systems.	
Information Asset Owner	General term for custodians or owners of a datasets, projects or other information assets within a TRE. For example, the owner of a dataset who has liaised with a TRE Operator on secure data ingress to the TRE.	Image datasets are appropriately catalogues, indexed, stored, monitored and auditable
Output Checker	People responsible for checking the disclosure risk of project outputs, before egress, as part of the disclosure control process. See Output management.	Checking research outputs, including images, are appropriately packaged and not disclosive Any potential for inferred disclosure is either eliminated or, as a minimum, mitigated to the best standards.

Table 3: Data Management Roles

Infrastructure Management Roles

Role name	Role description	Responsibilities
Operator	People responsible for the management of the TRE's IT infrastructure and general processes documented throughout the SATRE specification. Examples include carrying out data ingress/egress and managing user access. TRE operators should expect to have access to documentation regarding all processes they are required to carry out, developed by themselves or (in partnership with) the TRE Developers. This documentation should be comprehensive and include troubleshooting steps (see Knowledge management).	Ensuring images are appropriately transferred/made available in the SDE/TRE. Processes should be documented and auditable.
Developer	People responsible for building the software infrastructure that can be used as a TRE. These could be Research Software Engineers, whose job involves applying professional software engineering expertise to challenges in scientific research. Alternatively, these could be developers who are contracted to build a TRE for a given institution or project. TRE developers include people creating bespoke platforms catering to the specific requirements of a project or dataset, as well as developers building generalisable solutions to TRE provision that can be configured based on the research context.	Making research environments accessible with appropriate tools for image management and processing. Adhering to all relevant governance and data management principles relating to research environment provision.
Builder	People responsible for carrying out the Infrastructure Deployment Process. This role could be taken on by either the TRE Operators or the TRE Developers.	Making sure the research environments are appropriately patched, updated and made available. Processes should be documented and auditable.

Table 4: Infrastructure Management Roles

Governance Roles

Role name	Role description	Responsibilities
Information Governance Manager	People responsible for writing and/or compiling the correct operating procedures and policies for the TRE.	Creating and monitoring of the image de-identification and pre-processing activities.
Quality Manager	People responsible for ensuring the TRE is operating correctly, and all procedures and policies are being followed by other roles and work effectively. See Quality Management.	Ensuring any change management processes are followed, that processes follow available international, national, regional or local standards and research quality frameworks.
Top Management	People who lead and control an organisation at the highest level. This definition is taken from <i>ISO 9000:2015</i> and in this context refers to the most senior	Oversight of SDE/TRE processes and unblocking of any infrastructure

	governance official who own the risks associated with TRE research, can make decisions and allocate resources. See Risk Ownership Process.	and/or governance barriers hindering service development and provision.
Data Protection Manager	People responsible for data protection at the organisation hosting the TRE.	Review de-identification, processing and disclosure control checking processes for appropriateness and robustness.
Auditor	General IT term for people who evaluate an organisation's IT systems on whether they meet technology or cybersecurity regulatory requirements. For TREs, this may include requirements around sensitive data handling and information security controls. Auditors can be internal, or external people working for a consulting firm.	Auditing logs and process documentation to ensure image processing, de-identification, storage, management and disclosure control tasks are being appropriately performed and any non-conformities are logged, analysed and mitigated.

Table 5: Governance Roles

Public Roles

Role name	Role description	Responsibilities
Lay Panel	Members of the public charged with oversight of TRE operational decisions on behalf of parties affected by data usage.	Review research projects proposing to use imaging data and consider the potential for risks to disclosure and privacy
Data Subject	People who are identifiable by data being used for research, e.g., patients in healthcare record data.	Explicit consent and/or national opt-in or opt-out for research projects

Table 6: Public Roles

Summary

This guidance establishes an evidence-based framework for the preparation and governance of imaging data for research, informed by both literature and real-world implementation across NHS, academic, and industry settings. It demonstrates that challenges in imaging research are not isolated technical issues, but arise from the interaction between data quality, de-identification processes, governance frameworks, and infrastructure constraints.

The recommendations presented here provide a practical approach to addressing these challenges through:

- risk-proportionate de-identification
- context-specific definitions of image quality
- transparent and reproducible data processing
- alignment of governance and technical practices across organisations

A central finding is that decisions relating to image quality and anonymisation directly influence research outcomes, including bias, generalisability, and reproducibility. As such, governance

should be understood not only as a mechanism for protecting privacy, but as a key determinant of research integrity.

By integrating evidence with stakeholder experience, this guidance bridges the gap between high-level policy and operational practice. It provides a foundation for scalable, secure, and trustworthy imaging research, while identifying key areas for further development, including standardisation, validation, and cross-organisational alignment.

Appendix 1 – Research Imaging IG Checklist

This checklist operationalises the BESTIES principles and should be used alongside the detailed guidance provided in this document. This list is not prescriptive and should be used alongside any local or additional considerations.

Theme	Check		
Research Context	Research question clearly defined	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Imaging modality and data requirements justified	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Intended use of data specified (e.g., clinical research, AI training, validation)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Required level of data quality defined and fit-for-purpose	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Data Protection & De-identification	Data classification defined (identifiable/pseudonymised/anonymised)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Risk assessment completed (re-identification, misuse, data leakage)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	De-identification approach defined and justified	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Metadata reviewed for potential identifiers (including DICOM tags)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Impact of de-identification on data utility assessed	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Pixel data assessed for identifiers (e.g., burned-in text, overlays)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	De-identification process documented and version-controlled	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Validation of de-identification performed (technical and human review when needed)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Residual risk assessed and documented	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Cross-site consistency agreed or differences documented	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Data Quality	Data completeness assessed	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Image quality criteria defined and fit-for-purpose	<input type="checkbox"/>
Quality assessment method defined (manual or automated)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Metadata completeness assessed		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Data provenance captured and documented		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Annotation process defined (if applicable)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Inter-observer variability considered (if relevant)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Potential sources of bias identified (site, population, acquisition)		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Decisions to exclude or transform data documented		<input type="checkbox"/>	
Data Management & Infrastructure		Data pipeline defined (ingestion – processing – analysis – storage)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Tools and platforms identified (e.g., TRE/SDE, HPC)	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Access controls defined and implemented	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Data storage and transfer methods defined	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Audit logging in place	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Software and processing steps documented	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Version control applied to pipelines and datasets	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Governance & Compliance	Legal basis for data use confirmed	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Ethical approval obtained (if required)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Data sharing agreements in place (if required)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Roles and responsibilities clearly defined	<input type="checkbox"/>
	User access agreements in place	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Disclosure control processes defined	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Governance decisions documented and auditable	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sustainability & Reuse	Data custodianship defined	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Licensing and reuse permissions specified	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Consent for reuse confirmed	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Dataset documentation completed (e.g., PSD, data dictionary)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Metadata supports future reuse	<input type="checkbox"/>
	FAIR principles considered	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Long-term storage and access plan defined	<input type="checkbox"/>
Wider Considerations	Trade-offs documented (privacy vs utility, quality vs inclusion)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Decisions made using risk-proportionate approach	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Processes aligned across collaborating organisations (if required)	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Operational constraints (time, infrastructure, skills) considered	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Documentation sufficient for reproducibility	<input type="checkbox"/>